

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B307
Date: 16 July 2007
Take Off: 10:49:36
Landing: 12:47:37
Flight Time: 1h58m01s

Campaign: COPS

Operating Area: Baden-Baden, Germany

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Phil Brown	Met Office
5	Mission Scientist 2	Angela Dean	Leeds University
6	Flight Manager	Steve Devereau	FAAM
7	Cloud Physics	Jamie Trembath	FAAM
8	Core Chemistry / CCM2	Stuart Heath	FAAM
9	VACC 1	Barbara Brookes	Leeds University
10	CPI 1	James Dorsey	University of Manchester
11	CVI	Jeff Brown	Met Office
12	Nephelometers	Andy Wilson	Met Office
13	AMS	Will Morgan	University of Manchester
14			
15			
16			
17			
18			
19			
20			

Flight Track:

B307 Track 16-JUL-07

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B307
 Date: 16 July 2007
 Project: COPS
 Location: Baden Baden

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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103452		event	0.36 kft	164	INU to Nav
104133		event	0.36 kft	164	start taxi
104936		T/O	0.35 kft	212	Baden Baden
105356		event	6.0 kft	056	Nevzorov/JW zero
105705		Video	6.0 kft	030	FFC RFC start
110050	111309	Run 1.1	2.7 kft	216	
110511		event	2.7 kft	203	Heimann cal
111423	111652	Profile 1	2.7 - 5.6 kft	074	
111852		event	5.6 kft	032	Nev JW zero
111907	113045	Run 2.1	5.6 kft	008	
113452	114733	Run 3.1	2.6 kft	222	
114847	115141	Profile 2	2.6 - 5.6 kft	071	
115338	120612	Run 4.1	5.6 kft	004	
120748	121409	Profile 3	5.6 - 12.0 kft	199	
121510	121631	Profile 3	12.0 - 13.5 kft	295	
121738	121923	Profile 3	13.5 - 15.0 kft	032	
122255	122742	Profile 4	15.0 - 10.1 kft	201	
122909	123316	Profile 4	10.0 - 5.6 kft	355	
123749	124153	Run 5.1	5.6 kft	265	
124737		Land	0.39 kft	030	Baden Baden
125257		Shutdown	0.40 kft	156	48 46.91N 08 05.33E

B307 Track 16-JUL-07

EDSB -> EDDS - Overview

NavData Cycle 2007-7 Expires: Thursday, 02 August 2007.

Scale: 1:426851 (1 inch = 5.85 naut mi). Printed on 15 Jul 2007

JEPPESEN

FliteStar 9.2.0.2

PROJECT BRIEF: COPS - Convective and Orographically-induced Precipitation Study.

Scientific Aims: The goal of UK-COPS is to determine the properties of the aerosols that will likely be ingested into the convective clouds that form over the Black Forest mountains and to understand the formation and growth of ice and precipitation in these clouds . We wish to examine:

- the properties of the representative aerosol particles in the clear air that are transported into the convective clouds
- the concentration and size of cloud droplets just above cloud base
- the formation of the first ice due to primary nucleation on ice nuclei (IN)
- the development of ice via secondary processes such as the Hallett-Mossop process, in which new ice particles are generated during the riming growth of ice particles
- other secondary ice production processes, such as evaporative break-up;
- the production of supercooled raindrops and their role in the glaciation process
- the dependence of these processes on the dynamics of the cloud
- the production of precipitation

There will either be 2 flights per day: one in clear air to measure the properties of the aerosols and one later in the convective clouds; or the two parts will be flown in a single flight. Measurements will be made in cumulus clouds when their tops are about 0°C through to when the tops have grown to about -20°C.

Weather conditions:

Developing showers over the Black Forest mountains, Germany, within Box A and probably B.

Safety: Regions that paint RED on the aircraft weather radar should be avoided. No flight into clouds known to be producing lightning. There may be coordination with the DO-128 in Boxes A and B. The French and German Falcons may also be operating in the area.

Key instruments and their operation:

Basic meteorology

- Rosemount temperatures, GE hygrometer
- GPS, INU, turbulence probe. When in supercooled liquid water, Flight Manager or PIs should monitor turbulence probe and calibrated differential pressures for signs of icing (cessation of variability on signal).

Cloud Physics/Aerosol

- FFSSP, 2DC, 2DP, PCASP, CDP, CIP, SID-1 and SID-2. Normal monitoring to ensure correct operation. Operator should note particular features of interest eg. high concentrations, appearance of pristine ice crystal habits, appearance of large drops ($d > 100 \mu\text{m}$) in 2D imagery when above freezing level.
- CPI as above
- J-W LWC and Nevzorov LWC/TWC. Where straight/level and in clear air, these should be zeroed/calibrated and a note made in the Flight Managers log.
- TWC - profile ascents/descents should avoid cloud if possible
- AMS -
- CVI - below cloud base, normal operation is in aerosol mode; above cloud base, normal operation is in CVI mode
- VACC - in straight and level clear-air, 10 min runs; during cloud work and profiles, single temperature.

Sortie Brief: COPS – Convective and Orographically-induced Precipitation Study
Flight Number: B306
Date: 16 July 2007
Mission Scientists: Phil Brown and Alan Blyth
TO Time: 14:00 local

Sortie Aims: To measure properties of aerosols in the clear air and the development of convective clouds.

Sortie Location: Clear air in Rhine Valley and in convective clouds over Black Forest mountains. Leg over supersites.

Sortie Summary:

1. Characterise properties of aerosols in clear air at low levels.
2. Penetrate cumulus clouds preferably near the top of the cloud in the updraught. All cloud penetrations should be with *wings level*. Two principal options are:
 - A. stationary cloud or system of clouds;
 - B. several cumulus clouds either in area (low wind) or passing through the area.
3. Characterise properties of aerosols in detrainment layers around cloud.
4. Overfly supersites M, H and R.

Sortie Detail:

1. Out-of-Cloud: All changes in altitude at standard rates (1000 ft/min).
2 x Rhine Valley aerosol legs (70 mins)

2. Cloud work:

Note an important feature is to ascend with tops. This requires a non-standard ascent as fast as possible. Relay cloud top info to the DO-128.

Option A: Isolated developing clouds – ascend with the clouds near their top. All penetrations at constant altitude.

A.1 Proceed to about 0°C or top of cloud.

A.2 Adjust altitude to about 1000 ft below cloud top and penetrate cloud. The penetration should be made at a constant azimuth and altitude if possible. It is important to penetrate the growing turret in the updraught region. A few seconds after clearing cloud, turn and ascend for return to same region of cloud as quickly as possible using procedure turn.

A.3 Repeat A.2, ascending with the top (if appropriate) at the end of each penetration out of cloud, until FL200 or FL240, or cloud becomes too developed.

A.4 Repeat A.1 - A.3 for a new developing cumulus, go to **Option B**, or exit box.

Option B: Many developing cumulus clouds – sample clouds at constant altitude.

B.1 Proceed to 0°C

B.2 Commence 10 min runs (turning where appropriate) in along shear direction. Adjust track to randomly sample the updraught regions of growing turrets.

B.3 Ascend to -5°C (i.e. approximately 3500 ft) and repeat above for 10 min.

B.4 Repeat for -10°C, -15°C and -20°C if possible.

3. Detrainment layers

Proceed to level where cloud is being detrained from cloud and either make penetrations or circle around the cloud.

4. Leg over supersites Murg Valley (M), Hornisgrinde (H) and Achern (R) at about 5500 ft if in clear air. (15 min)

B307

16/07/2007

Mission Scientist Debrief:

Phil Brown

1. Assessment of flight

Climbout to 6000ft in preparation for low level legs. Descent to 2700ft for start of southbound aerosol sampling leg in the Rhine valley. This is within elevated stable layer above the well-mixed surface layer. Almost no wind. Large variations of aerosol concentration along the leg, possible connected to convective plumes rising from below.

Climb to 5600ft for northbound leg over the Black Forest. Cumulus present but no signs of vertical development at this time. Dry convective turbulence along track and the main cloud region is to the east of this track. Dew point very variable along the run and the top of an aerosol layer appears to be above this altitude.

On second southbound leg at 2600ft, very similar structures are seen in aerosol variables – possible plumes from somewhere? Further N-bound leg at 5600ft, again with similar T/Td structure to that seen previously.

Profile ascent into the box A/B region to FL150. Cloudbase at ~8200ft – lower than yesterday – but quite broken. Clouds growing from elevated boundary layer over the mountains. There is a stable layer at about 13500ft -1.0C and very dry above (Td ~ -35C) which is inhibiting any further cloud growth.

Sortie curtailed as it is clear that no deeper convection will occur.

Profile descent to 5600ft for run out over supersites M, H and R.

2. Summary of weather conditions

Ridge axis to east of COPS area with upper SW flow. Surface ridge extending over the area with v light surface winds.

Convection developing over the BF driven by diurnal surface heating, but suppressed by stable layer at just above the freezing level.

TIME	DETAILS
1148	take of FKB. Some Cu just forming over the BF. initially appears to be at S and N edges of the box A/B.
110050	RM at 2700ft. Sfc. layer is below 950mb
1105	2700ft. 917mb, within elevated stable layer above the sfc. layer. almost no wind
1110	next leg might be in much drier layer.
1107	plume of high cone CWC counts here.
111308	end R1.1 - high CWC & Td - sfc layer air
1114	start P1 2700 to 5500, more stable at S end.
111907	start 2.1 5600ft. cloudbase lower than yesterday? No sign of vertical development at this time.
1121	Dry convective turbulence. cloud line is again to the east of this track.
1127	Turb continues.
112906	Td very variable along run. Top of aerosol layer seems to be above us.
113452	Start 3.1 2600ft. @ FKB Profiles consistent with initial climbout.
	CWC initially high but back to ~6000 cm ⁻³ typically in mid layer above sfc.
114733	End 3.1 aerosol fluctuations consistent on all instruments.
114817	Start P2 2600 - 5600ft. cloud formation is to N of this leg, but most of it S. of the box.
115338	Start 4.1 5600ft. (1014)
	Note T/Td structure of 1.1 & 3.1 v. similar. also CWC.
120035	T/Td on this leg also reproducing 2.1.
	End 4.1
	8200ft cloudbase, but somewhat broken.
121510	P3 recon at F120

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MISSION SCIENTIST: P2/2

Time

Details.

1217

Clouds based in elevated moisture layer.

1220

FL150 at top of profile. V-dry Td 33.5
 Stable layer at 610 mb and dryness
 will be inhibiting any vertical development.

122254

PL₄ FL150 →

123315

end PL₄ 5600 ft. - for supersite run.

123749

Start run at M in tower.

O/H H.

End Run o/h R.

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B307 **T/O:** 10:49:36
Date of flight: 16/07/07 **Land:** 12:47:37

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		To exeter
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to processing PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt		hh = Last sec processed =
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS		File size =
3) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (see comment box)</i> e) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Use time just before/after take-off/landing. If T/O /landing just after/before the hour, ensure start/end time is before/after the hour if there is an FFSSP_hh.txt file for that hour.
4) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: <i>Use the most recent calibration file.</i> Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)		Total glitches = Sec file written ok? Note calibration file used Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) FLOODS> WAVE a) WAVE> write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto b) WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Note time correction applied to FFSSP by /auto =
6) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY (y=x+1) d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		Input file size = M5 output file size =
7) CHECKS: i). Are FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC synchronized in time? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>JW LWC para 535</i> <i>Nevzorov LWC para 602</i> <i>FFSSP LWC para 1202</i> ii). If not, repeat from step 5b replacing /auto with addt=x which adds x+20 secs to FFSSP time.		Synchronized?

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B307
Date of Flight: 16/07/07

B) 2D PROCESSING		REPROCESS +1hr
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC	Y	
2) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip)	Y	
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS	Y	8358 blocks
4) Log on to FLOODS		
5) Unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.zip	Y	Size of Bnnn.dat = 90585
6) FLOODS> WAVE WAVE> CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.dat b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat WAVE> exit	Y	Use PVWAVE for this section Blocks read = 24152 Blocks written = 24152 Bad reads = 0
7) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE a) Default directory: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat d) Comment string: e) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 5 min)</i> f) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land + 5 min)</i> g) Read 2DC: Y h) Read 2DP: Y i) Secondary data: Y j) FSP-SYNC: Y k) cmd.str: Y l) Auto time correction: N m) Full length secondary: N	Y	Start = 10:45:00 End = 12:50:00 Ignore error message scroll (vestigial error from tapes) Are FRW, FSP, IMB, PCA,SEC files in PMSDATA? Y Are they non-zero in size? AUX, IMB = 0blocks
8) FLOODS> WAVE i). WAVE> imagedisplay a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) File generation no: 0 d) Time from IWC plot: N e) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP f) Start time: <i>As in 7e above</i> g) End time: <i>As in 7f above</i> h) Time interval (sec): 5 recommended (0 for all images) ii). WAVE> auto_image a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 1 min)</i> e) Enter end time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 1 min)</i> f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks: 10 iii). WAVE> exit to create files iv). FTP ascii *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC v). Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter vi). Output as pdf file (720 dpi resolution), appending name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files	N	2D image display and printing Must be done from FLOODS itself. Note any problems with images No images to display as no AUX records Prepare imagery for Core data From own PC again Start = 104500 End = 125000 FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_ Bnnn_2Dx-images.ps Notes on this in instructions

<p>9) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO</p> <p>a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: <i>Hit enter</i> d) Time correction: <i>Time offset of the 2D data</i> e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both <i>0 unless either probe known to be faulty</i> h) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O + 30sec)</i> i) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 30sec)</i> j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type 2DC: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud l) Particle type 2DP: 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown m) Coefficient choice: 2 n) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D</p>	N	<p>NB. an error message may appear, floating point exception, rerun and use time quoted in error message, repeat until successful.</p> <p>X =</p> <p>Start = End =</p> <p>Time data processed to =</p> <p>2dproc files present? *.2dc, *.2dp and *.dat</p>
<p>10) FLOODS> WAVE</p> <p>i) WAVE> WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D' ii). exit</p>	N	<p>Use PVWAVE for this section</p> <p>Error message about HDDR file should be ignored.</p> <p>Records =</p>
<p>11) FLOODS> MODIFY</p> <p>a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default</p>	N	<p>X = Y = (X+1)</p>
<p>12) CHECKS:</p> <p>Are 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Nevzerov TWC para 605</i> <i>2DC IWC para 1302</i> <i>2DP IWC para 1312</i></p>	N	<p>Correlated?</p>

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B307
Date of Flight: 16/07/07

C) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:	Y	
2) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW a) Flight number: Bnnn b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii) d) Minimum size channel: <i>default = 1</i> <i>If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here</i> e) Calibration volume flow rate: <i>Use the most recent value. (1.15ccs⁻¹ Feb 07)</i> <i>Calibration files to be stored in Exeter</i> <i>Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm³s⁻¹</i> f) Time correction: <i>Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9d</i> g) Start time: <i>0 if unknown</i> h) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Min size = 2 Vol flow rate = 1.0 105000 124700
3) FLOODS> WAVE i).WAVE> write_procpcasp_to_m5, 'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat', 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp' ii). WAVE> exit	Y	Use PVWAVE for this section
4) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>	Y	X = b307_tas Y = X+1 = b307_tas_pcasp
5) CHECKS Are PCASP and JW peaks synchronous? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Neph – total blue scatter.</i> <i>PCASP conc para 1550</i>	N	Data present Merged OK? Can't check easily

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B307**

 Date **16/7/07**

 Operator's name: **A.W**

 Page **1** of **1**

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
103000								PREFLIGHT OK
110000		2500ft	12.4	36	32	—	15C	Positioning after take off.
110050	1-1	2700	12.7	38	34	↗	15	Start R1.1 Set water to +45
110440			10.2	39	69	↗	43	Set flow to 10.2
110730			8	41.6	76	—	45	Set flow to 8
111309			15.8	43	83	↘	45	end of run. set water to +15 & flow to 15
111423	P1	2700 ↗						Start P1 ↗
111652	P1	5600ft	13.8	14	50	↘	27.7	end P1
111907	2-1	—	9.5	22	46	↗	23	Start run 2.1, ramping up, flow rate down.
		—	14.6	20.7	77	↘	45	ramping down + increasing flow.
113045	2-1	—	14.6	26	39	↘	20	end run.
113452	3-1	2600ft	9.5	38	38.2	↗	17.8	Start run. ramp up, flow down
114200	↗	—	14.7	38	78.6	↘	44	ramping down. flow up.
114723	—	—	14.8	50	50.4	↘	22	end Run
114847	P2	↗	14.4	45.1	47.1	↘	18.6	Start P2 ↗
115141	—	5600ft	13.5	15.8	31.2		15.2	end P2
115338	4-1	—	9.3	26.9	30.8	↗	11.6	Start Run, ramp up, flow down.
120150		—	16.1	24.6	78.6	↘	45	ramp down flow up
120612	4-1	—	16.1	29.8	44	↘	24.6	end Run. Drain system
								end Wet Neph Science

B307 CVI log

7/16/07 11:34:44 AM despite several re-starts unable to get pcasp to work
7/16/07 11:35:05 AM run 3.1
7/16/07 11:53:39 AM run 4.1
7/16/07 12:08:15 PM profile climb

Flight:

B307

KEY

- Duff Data
- Minor Problems
- OK
- Not Fitted
- Fitted, Not Operated

Thermometers

- Cabin Temperature:
- Heimann:
- Deiced Temp:
- Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

- FWVS:
- General Eastern:
- Johnson Williams:
- Nevezorov:
- Total Water Probe:

Cameras

- Downward Facing:
- Forward Facing:
- Rearward Facing:
- Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

- Cruciform GPS:
- GIN Applanix:
- INU Honeywell:
- Radar Altimeter:
- RVSM IAS:
- RVSM Static Pressure:
- XR5 GPS:

Report Created 20/08/2007
17:26:52

Misc Core

- AMTG:
- AVAPS:
- Cabin Pressure:
- Fax machine:
- Printer:
- S9 Static Pressure:
- Satcom C:
- Satcom H:
- Turb Centre-Static:
- Turb Left Right:
- Turb Up-Down:
- Turb Horizontal Chk:
- Turb Vertical Chk:
- Weather Radar:

DLUs:

- DLU AERACK:
- DLU BBR Lower:
- DLU BBR Upper:
- DLU Core Chem:
- DLU Core Consoles:
- DLU Port Aft:
- DLU Port Fwd:
- DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

- BBR (clear) Lower:
- BBR (IR) Lower:
- BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

- BBR (clear) Upper:
- BBR (IR) Upper:
- BBR (red) Upper:

- ARIES:
- DEIMOS:
- IR Camera:
- JNO2 Lower:
- JNO2 Upper:
- JO1D Lower:
- JO1D Upper:
- MARSS:
- SHIMS Lower:
- SHIMS Upper:
- SWS:
- TAFTS:

Last Updated:

Cloud Probes

- 2DC:
- 2DP:
- FFSSP:
- PCASP:
- ADA:
- CCN:
- CDP:
- CIP 100:
- CIP 25:
- CPI:
- CVI:
- SID1:
- SID2:
- Aerosol**
- CPC 3025A:
- Filters 47mm:
- Filters 90mm:
- Neph - Dry:
- Neph - Wet:
- PSAP:
- AMS:
- CPC 3025 (AMS):
- INC:
- VACC:
- CPC 3010A (CVI):

01/08/2007 12:09:56

Chemistry

- CO Aerolaser 5002:
- NOx TE42C:
- Ozone TE49C:
- Ozone TE49:
- SO2 TE43C:
- TDLAS (NIR) CH4:
- TDLAS (NIR) CO2:
- FAGE:
- Formaldehyde:
- NOxy:
- ORAC:
- PAN:
- PERCA:
- Peroxide:
- PTRMS:
- TDLAS (1C):
- WAS Bags:
- WAS Bottles:
- Misc Non-Core**
- CASI/ATM:
- LIDAR:
- LTI:
- SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B307

Date: 16/07/2007

Instruments

FFSSP failure, out of range voltage

CVI PCASP: suspected comms problem with CVI PC.

Aircraft

None

Satcom-H Calls

Dornier crew

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: 16/7/07

Flight No: 3307

Pre-Flighter:

No.	✓ or x	<u>Location</u>	<u>Action</u>	<u>Comments</u>
1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Hangar	Collect Dustbin, put on a/c	
<u>Aircraft Cabin: Power-up</u>				
2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	
3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Aft CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
6	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
7	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Recording data	
8	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
9	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
10	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
11	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
12	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GPS	Checked	
13	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Align	
14	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	
16	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	
17	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	FWVS	Set up	Not fitted
18	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	
19	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked / Set	
20	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
21	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC	ON & Checked	STATUS NOT FLASHING
22	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Balance checked	
23	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Navigate then back to Align	
24	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Hubs x 4	Checked ON	
25	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd Console	Miss. Sci Laptop CB made	& CB on Port Fwd SSP
26	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CNC	Butanol filled	
27	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Dry Neph	Power up & Zero Cal	ANDY WILSON TO PERFORM AS HIS PREFLIGHT
28	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CGPS	Set up	
29	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	
			Proceed to External Checks	
				→ DONE MANUALLY - NETWORK PROGS.
				→ SD TO BRININ
External Checks overleaf				→

7:49
 5040
 216
 5040
 210

Pre-Flighter's Log

No.	<u>√ or x</u>	<u>Location</u>	<u>Action</u>	<u>Comments</u>
<u>External Checks</u>				
29	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	<div style="text-align: right; margin-bottom: 5px;"><i>BW</i></div> <hr/>
30	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
31	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
32	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
34	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
35	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
36	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
37	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
38	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
39	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	All other covers	Removed	
40	<input type="checkbox"/>	Dustbin	Returned to hangar	
41	<input type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
42	<input type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Avalon informed	
<u>Avalon Checks</u>				
43	<input type="checkbox"/>	Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		Signed
44	<input type="checkbox"/>	ICEX applied		
45	<input type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe - Traps emptied, detail contents -		a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) 1/4 full or more
46	<input type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe - Traps dried and resealed		

Flight B307 12:32:25

Heading 17 deg Speed 232 knots Height 6.5kft Press 796mb

Lat 48°36.0'N Long 8°18.0'E Wind 8 ms-1/ 158 deg

Temp 15.35C Dewpoint 3.04C

From 11:32:03 to now

Current values			
++++	PRESSURE HEIGHT	1987.06	m
	CNC COUNTS	3370	p cm-3

Flight B307 12:27:31

Heading 205 deg Speed 253 knots Height 10.2kft Press 689mb

Lat 48°24.0'N Long 8°18.0'E Wind 8 ms-1/ 192 deg

Temp 5.41C Dewpoint -2.91C

From 10:49:21 to now

	Current values		
	STATIC PRESSURE	689.28	mb
++++	DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP	5.41	deg C
++++	DEW POINT	-2.92	deg C

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B307:

Log	Reason
Core Chemistry	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
VACC	VACC operator does not create a log sheet
PSAP log	No log as PSAP pump/filter info included on Flight Summary page
AMS	Log only of interest to instrument operator so no copy left with FAAM
CPI	CPI operator does not create a log sheet

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	22 Aug 2007	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1	15 Jan 2008	Doug Anderson	Updated video tape holder information
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

1 x Rearward Facing Cameras

1 x Forward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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